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Fertility restoration studies in four WA CMS lines of rice

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Fertility restoration studies involving four wild abortive (WA) cytoplasmic male sterile (CMS) lines—V20A, IR58025A, IR62829A, and IR54752A—resulted in the identification of 20 restorers. We studied segregation for fertility in the F_2 and backcross progenies of these CMS lines with four restorer lines—ARC11353, IR30864, IR13419-113-3, and IR9761-19-1. The results indicated that fertility restoration in WA CMS lines was controlled by two additive major genes. Their effect was sporophytic and they displayed differential gene interactions such as epistasis with complete dominance (12:3:1) or epistasis with incomplete dominance (9:6:1) depending on the parents involved in the cross.

We noticed differential segregation of the F_2 and backcross progenies in the crosses involving IR30864 and IR9761-19-1 depending on the female parent. This suggested that the performance and expressivity of the R genes varied according to the nuclear background of

the female parent. The pattern of segregation in crosses involving IR54752A was different from that of other CMS lines, suggesting the involvement of certain minor genes for fertility restoration carried by this CMS line in deciding the fertility of the progenies. ■

Effect of minor genes in restoration of fertility in CMS lines of rice

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We evaluated 128 hybrids in the 1994 dry season and 135 hybrids in the 1995 wet season. The hybrids, involving varieties C29 and PMK2, with different wild abortive (WA) sources of cytoplasmic male sterile (CMS) lines—IR58025A, IR62829A, and PMS3A—showed marked differences in pollen and spikelet fertility. When C29 was crossed with IR62829A and PMS3A, it behaved as a partial restorer (21-90% pollen and spikelet fertility). But when crossed with IR58025A, it behaved as a maintainer (100% pollen and spikelet sterility). All three CMS lines, however, had WA cytoplasm. Similarly, PMK2 behaved as a restorer (>90% pollen and

spikelet fertility) with PMS3A, while it maintained sterility (100%) with IR62829A. The minor or modifier genes present in the pollinator might have reacted with the CMS lines used and resulted in this type of variation. ■

Breeding for male fertility restoration incorporating Basmati rice quality

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Basmati is the most highly valued rice commodity in the world agricultural trade market. Pusa Basmati 1, released in India, combines both high yield and ideal Basmati quality. In Pakistan, semi-tall Pak 385 and Pak 386 are reported to be better yielding than Basmati 370. Results at IARI have demonstrated the possibility of developing hybrids with Basmati grain quality and a high level of heterosis. Such Basmati hybrids would raise yields further.

A major limitation to developing Basmati rice hybrids is the nonavailability of satisfactory restoration among Basmati cultivars or breeding lines. Some 90% of Basmati materials showed imperfect maintaining ability, 3%

showed good maintenance, and 7% showed partial restoration. But few showed 60-70% restoration ability. This situation led us to begin a systematic restorer breeding program incorporating ideal Basmati quality.

Testcrosses were made using cytoplasmic male sterile (CMS) lines Pusa 1127A (a new cyto sterility source from Pusa 743), Pusa 3A wild abortive (WA), and IR58025A (WA) with the Basmati cultivar or breeding line that had shown high F_1 fertility (60-70%) in previous testcrosses. All the F_1 s were raised. Seeds from the best fertile plants were harvested and subjected to grain and cooking quality tests. Only those hybrids that exhibited Basmati cooking characteristics in an appreciable proportion of grains were raised to the F_2 generation. Selections were made on the basis of spikelet fertility, grain shape, and grain appearance. They were subjected to cooking quality tests and only those possessing ideal Basmati characteristics were raised to the F_3 . In the F_3 , diverse-looking plants were selectively intermated and the entire process was repeated. Simultaneously, some of these selected plants were testcrossed with Pusa 3A. Pollen donor plants of hybrids showing improved restoration and ideal Basmati quality were advanced to the F_4 . In the F_4 and later generations, the entire process was again repeated as in the F_3 . Likewise, the material was advanced to the F_6 generation. The intermated lines were also advanced to further generations.

Testcrosses made between Pusa 3A and the selected lines revealed that nine lines—Sps95-694-2, Sps95-694-3, Sps95-81-1, Sps95-81-3, Sps95-81-4, Sps95-81-5, Sps95-81-6, Sps95-768, and Sps95-167-1—showed normal restoration. The grain quality of these hybrids was comparable with that of Pusa Basmati 1 and Karnal Local. Three of these lines are now used for Basmati hybrid seed production with Pusa 3A (Basmati CMS line). ■

Genetics of thermo-sensitive genic male sterile lines in rice

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Understanding the inheritance pattern and studying allelic relations among diverse thermosensitive genic male sterile lines (TGMS) were the objectives of this investigation. Lines F61, SA2, JP1, JP8-8-1s, ID24, and IC10, developed at the DRR, Hyderabad, and lines IR32364, IR68292, IR68294, IR68945, and IR68949, received from IRRI, Philippines, were crossed with a set of normal pollen parents, to study segregation patterns in the F_2 , F_3 , and backcross generations. The results indicated that sterility caused by the TGMS trait was governed by a single recessive gene. In segregating populations, however, individual TGMS progenies from the same F_2 showed different fertility levels. This indicated that some other genes modify the major gene and affect fertility.

Allelic relations were examined by studying direct crosses and backcrosses involving two different TGMS lines over seasons. The lines developed from Norin PL 12 (*tms2*) (IR68292, IR68294, IR68945, and IR68949) at IRRI were allelic to ID24 and JP1. The lines IR32364 (*tms3*), JP8-8-1s, and IC10 were also allelic. Lines SA2 and F61 were observed to be nonallelic to all other lines, and may possess different TGMS genes, including *tms1* from China. ■

Mitochondrial gene expression in cytoplasmic male sterile and fertile lines of rice

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In various plant species, rearrangements in the mitochondrial genome have been associated with cytoplasmic male sterility (CMS). These rearrangements could modify genome expression and thereby play a role in pollen abortion. In rice, investigations carried out in our laboratory have established some rearrangements in the genetic organization of mitochondrial DNA between male sterile and fertile lines. For example, the *cox1* locus was found rearranged in the CMS line compared with the fertile lines.

To establish the correlation, if any, in DNA organizational pattern with the expression of the male sterile phenotype, we conducted a Northern analysis on total RNA from the sterile and fertile lines. The blot, when probed with *atp6*, showed a single transcript in all the lines tested, whereas *atp9* and *cox3/orf25* showed five and two transcripts, respectively. On probing with *atp9*, we observed multiple transcripts of sizes 3.2 kb, 1.7 kb, 1.3 kb, 0.8 kb, and 0.6 kb, and 0.3 kb was the most abundant of the transcripts, probably representing the mature functional transcript. The cotranscribed genetic locus of *cox3/orf25* when used as a probe, yielded two transcripts of 2 kb and 1 kb. Even though *atp6* in Chinsurah Boro-type cytoplasm has been found to be differentially transcribed and edited, and hence implicated in CMS, we could not detect different transcripts of *atp6* in the rice lines used in our study bearing WA type cytoplasm. Work on putting more probes on the Northern blots and studying the gene-specific pattern of expression is in progress. ■